

PRINCIPALS' APPLICATION OF MANAGERIAL SKILLS AS A CORRELATE OF TEACHERS' JOB PERFORMANCE IN SECONDARY SCHOOLS IN ANAMBRA STATE, NIGERIA

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Abstract:

The study investigated principals' application of managerial skills as a correlate of teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State. Three research questions guided the study and three hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance. Correlational research design was utilized for the study. The population of the study consisted of all the 5,286 teachers in public secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. A sample size of 759 teachers were drawn using proportionate stratified sampling technique. Two sets of researcher-developed instruments titled "Principals Application of Managerial Skills Scale (PAMSC) and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ) were utilized for data collection. The instruments were face validated by three experts and subjected to reliability test estimate using Cronbach alpha which yielded 0.68, 0.71 and 0.68 for parts A, B and C of PAMSC respectively and the reliability index of 0.68 was obtained for TJPQ. Pearson' Product Moment Co-efficient were used to answer the research questions, whereas the hypotheses were tested using t-test. The findings of the study as indicated among others revealed that there is a high relationship between principals' application of communication skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State. It was also revealed that there was significant relationship between principals' application of interpersonal relationship skills and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State. Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that Post Primary School Service Commission should introduce a school-based annual training programme in all secondary schools for principals to up-date their communication skills to enhance teachers' job performance.

Keywords: principals, managerial skills, communication skills, supervisory skills, interpersonal relationship skills and teachers' job performance

1. Introduction

Education is a positive instrument for the overall improvement of one's knowledge, ideologies and skills with the aim of achieving self-reliance, sustainability and enlightenment. It is also the key for the development of one's personality and as such inculcates the right character in accordance with acceptable societal norms and values. Oluremi (2016) stressed that education is a means through which individuals acquire the relevant knowledge, skill, and values to ensure proper intellectuals, character development for self-reliance and responsible citizenship. Formal education which is received in school system are in three levels namely; primary, secondary and tertiary education. The secondary education is managed by the principal. Nwogu and Ebonu (2019) stressed that principals are the managers of secondary schools, the managerial skills they possess play critical role in ensuring operational efficiency of their respective schools.

There are several definitions of managerial skills based on scholars' views and perceptions of the concept. According Sayed, Amin, Tehrani and Ali (2010) defined managerial skills as specialised technical knowledge in certain jobs that managers possess to enable them perform their duties and roles. Sayed et al added that it is a set of behaviour that leads to effective job performance. According to Egboka, Ezeugbor and Enueme (2013), managerial skills of school leaders refer to their ability to successfully plan, organize, co-ordinate, control, make decisions and initiate actions to aid the effective management of schools. Managerial skills involves competence and ability of the principals to make decisions, initiate action control and stimulate teachers to achieve predetermined goals. The managerial skills possessed by principals enable them to plan, delegate, stimulate and control the activities of teachers. There are many components of managerial skills. Muraina (2014) noted that managerial skills include; communication skills, supervisory skills and organizational skills. Memisoglu (2015) identified managerial skills as; conceptual skills, technical skills and interpersonal skills. However, this study will focus on these aspects of managerial skills namely; communication skills, interpersonal skills and supervisory skills.

Communication is seen as the ability of the communicator to successfully exchange information and ideas between two or more people through the means of speaking, listening, writing, body expression, symbolic signs or any other means as deemed fit by the sender. Akinwale and Okotoni (2018) pointed out that for better communication in a school, the principal must first conceive ideas and relate such ideas to the staff and other stakeholders. Akinwale and Okotoni further added that the principal is responsible for sharing visions and useful information needed for the smooth running of the school as well as transfer ideas and feelings to enhance the collaborative support of all individuals within the school. Dissemination of information and exchange of ideas require communication skills. Communication skills is the ability or competency of principals to exchange ideas and disseminate information to their subordinates in a timely and accurate manner. According to Manafa (2018), communication skills entails speaking

appropriately to people while maintaining good eye contact, eloquent speech with tailored language, listening effectively, writing clearly with concise language, being confident, friendliness, empathy, use of question, open mindedness and presenting your ideas appropriately. According to Abbass (2014), communication skill is vital because members of staff need to know what they are expected to do, what standards of performance are expected of them and how long they have to do any job assigned to them. Manafa (2018) in addition, asserted that poor usage of communication skills in secondary schools in Anambra State has been a great concern to the school management and members of staff. Manafa further observed that most school principals refuse to have listening ears to the members of staff and also not competent to use clear and brief and straight forward language while giving out informing, there by bringing confusion, tension and conflicts in the school.

Interpersonal relationship skill is concerned with the ability of school managers to interact and work together with the subordinates to achieve school's set goals and objectives. Giami and Obiechina (2019) asserted that interpersonal relationship skill includes the ability to work with people in order to motivate and inspire them. The interpersonal skills applied by principals enable them to associate well with their subordinates and this provides the opportunity for the smooth running of the school's affairs. Werang (2014) stated that interpersonal skills enables a leader to influence team or groups to work together to accomplish organizational goals and objectives. Interpersonal skills enables principals to become sensitive and empathetic to what motivates teachers, create an atmosphere of trust and put into consideration the needs of teachers when deciding on how to achieve the school objectives. Ayeni (2014) stressed that interpersonal skills are important attributes in maintaining a positive work atmosphere, without these skills relationship in school organization becomes hostile and in-turn resulting to staff dissatisfaction.

Similar to this, Okpe (2018) noted that supervision of teachers' instructional activities is very important as it helps to guide, direct and stimulate growth with the aim of improving teaching and learning. Through instructional supervision, teachers are assisted to improve on their strengths and overcome their weaknesses. This act also stimulates the professional growth and professional development of the teachers. Zachariah (2013) stressed that the essential supervisory skills required of school administrators include the ability to; solve instructional problem, building upon strengths of staff members, observe teachers in the classroom, design an instrument for evaluating instruction, analyze teaching, monitor teaching performance and adjust supervisory guidance on the basis of that monitoring among others. Rand cited in Okpe (2018) also listed supervisory skills to include: motivation, demonstration, varsity and generalization differences, problem solving and self-discovery. These skills enable secondary school principals to develop and build teachers' collegiality and collaboration in the instructional supervision process. It is worrisome that Uzoechina and Nwankwo (2017) observed that most principals in Anambra state hardly make efforts to develop a community of professional teachers' with a sense of collegiality and collaboration during

the instructional supervision. Umaru and Aliyu (2018) corroborating this, that in spite of the societal demand for thorough supervision of instruction to improve teachers' job performance in schools, there is a growing concern about the realization of such secondary education objectives due to doubt that many principals give little attention to supervision of instructional activities in secondary schools in Nigeria.

Teachers' job performance are those duties or tasks accomplished or executed by the teaching staff at a particular period in the school system. Achmad (2017) defined teachers' job performance as the result achieved in carrying out the tasks assigned to them, based on their skills, experience, sincerity, and the time available. The teachers' job performance is determined by various activities or tasks executed by teaching staff. Uzoehina and Oguegbu (2015) noted that the level of teachers' job performance is determined in the under-listed teachers' activities; regular and punctual report to school and classes, ability to cooperate with the principal to achieve school the set objectives, readiness to accept extra responsibilities the principal endorses, keen interest in supervising students classroom works, respects school guidelines and patterns of performing tasks, teaches in assigned classrooms, plans and prepares lessons, attends school meetings whenever they are convened as well as PTA meetings, supervises students' extra-curricular activities, keeps accurate records of the learners' level of progress, sets, marks, and assesses written works among others.

In as much as there seems to be outstanding teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State, there is still need for improvement through embracing principals' managerial skills. However, unsatisfactory state of affairs in some secondary schools in Anambra State may be attributed to lapses in principals' application of managerial skills. Manafa (2018) observed that principals are lacking in competency to listen, use clear, brief and straight forward language in communicating with staff and this result to confusion, tensions and conflicts in secondary schools in Anambra State. The tensions and conflicts adversely affect interpersonal relationship among principals and teachers. The cases of absenteeism, persistent lateness and other form of professional misconduct may indicate lapses in principals' managerial skills to control the teachers' activities. To buttress this, Okoye, Onyali and Ezeugbor (2016) observed that there exists in schools, inadequate supervision and some principals haphazardly discharge their supervisory function which makes teachers indolent in their duty posts. It is based on this problem that this study was undertaken.

2. Purpose of the Study

The main purpose of the study is to ascertain principals' application of managerial skills as a correlates of teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State. Specifically, this study sought to find out:

- 1) The relationship between principals' application of communication skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State.

- 2) The relationship between principals' application of interpersonal relationship skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State.
- 3) The relationship between principals' application of supervisory skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State.

2.1 Research Questions

The following research questions guided the study:

- 1) What is the relationship between principals' application of communication skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State?
- 2) What is the relationship between principals' application of interpersonal relationship and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State?
- 3) What is the relationship between principals' application of supervisory skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State?

2.2 Hypotheses

The following hypotheses were tested at 0.05 level of significance:

- 1) There is no significant relationship between principals' application of communication skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State.
- 2) There is no significant relationship between principals' application of interpersonal relationship skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State.
- 3) There is no significant relationship between principals' application of supervisory skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State.

3. Method

Correlation research design was adopted for the study. According to Nworgu (2015), this type of study seeks to establish what relationship exists between two or more variables. This design is appropriate since the study seeks to collect data from respondents in order to investigate principals' application of managerial skills as a correlates of teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. The study was carried out in secondary schools in Anambra State, Nigeria. The population of the study comprised 5,286 public secondary school teachers in Anambra State. Proportionate stratified sampling technique was utilized to draw 793 teachers for the study.

Two sets of researchers-developed instruments titled "Principals Application of Managerial Skills Scale (PAMSC) and Teachers' Job Performance Questionnaire (TJPQ) were utilized for data collection. The instruments were developed from various related literature reviewed, personal observation of the researchers and interaction with experts in the education sector. PAMSC is made of three clusters namely; A, B and C. Section A which centred on communication skill contained seven items, Section B contains nine

Items on interpersonal relationship skill and Section C which focused on supervisory skill contains 11 items. PAMSC contains twenty seven items. On the other hand, TJPQ contains twelve items. The two sets of instrument (PAMSC and TJPQ) were structured on four-point rating scale of Strongly Agree (SA), Agree (A), Disagree (D); Strongly Disagree (SD) and weighted 4, 3, 2 and 1 respectively.

Two sets of researchers-developed instruments were subjected to face validation. In order to ensure face validation of the instruments, the title, purpose of the study, research questions and drafted copy of the instruments were presented to three experts who are lecturers in Faculty of Education, Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. Two of the experts were from the Department of Educational Management and Policy and the other a specialist in Measurement and Evaluation, Department of Educational Foundations. Based on their comments and suggestions, the instrument was modified. The reliability of PAMSC and TJPQ were determined after administering the copies of the instruments to 30 secondary school teachers in Enugu State. The data collected were subjected to measure of internal consistency using Cronbach alpha which yielded the reliability index of 0.68, 0.71 and 0.68 for parts A, B and C of PAMSC respectively and the reliability index of 0.68 was obtained for TJPQ.

Data were collected through face-to-face method by the researchers together with four research assistants who were briefed on the purpose of the study and their roles in ensuring collection of valid data. Out of 793 copies of the two set of instruments distributed, 778 were duly filled and retrieved indicating 98% return rate. Pearson's Product Moment Correlation Coefficient to answer the research questions and t-test statistical tool was used to test the hypotheses. For decisions on the research questions, the coefficient (r) and the size of the relationship was interpreted using the interpretation of correlation coefficient by Downie and Heath cited in Nworgu (2015) as shown: 0.80 and above for high, above 0.30-below 0.80 for moderate and 0.30 and below for low respectively. For decisions on the hypotheses, if t-calculated is equal to or greater than t-critical at 0.05 level of significance, the null hypothesis is rejected, but if otherwise, it is not rejected.

4. Results

Research Question 1: What is the relationship between principals' application of communication skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 1: Pearson's Correlation between principals' application of communication skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools

N		Communication Skill	Teachers' job Performance	Decision
Communication Skill	778	1	.871	High
Teachers' Job Performance	778	.871	1	

Table 1 shows that the Pearson's Correlation Coefficient, $r. (778) = .871$. This is an indication that there is a high relationship between principals' application of communication skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 2: What is the relationship between principals' application of interpersonal relationship skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 2: Pearson's Correlation between principals' application of communication skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools

N		Interpersonal Relationship Skill	Teachers' job Performance	Decision
Interpersonal Relationship Skill	778	1	.711	Moderate
Teachers' Job Performance	778	.711	1	

Table 2 shows that the Pearson's Correlation Coefficient, $r. (778) = .711$. This is an indication that there is a moderate relationship between principals' application of interpersonal relationship skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Research Question 3: What is the relationship between principals' application of supervisory skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State?

Table 3: Pearson's Correlation between principals' application of supervisory skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools

N		Supervisory Skill	Teachers' job Performance	Decision
Supervisory Skill	778	1	.867	High
Teachers' Job Performance	778	.867	1	

Table 3 shows that the Pearson's Correlation Coefficient, $r. (778) = .867$. This is an indication that there is a high relationship between principals' application of supervisory skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State.

H₀₁: There is no significant relationship between principals' application of communication skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 4: t-test analysis of no significant relationship
 between application of communication skill and teachers' job performance

N		Communication Skill	Teachers' Job Performance	t-cal.	t-crit.	Remark
Communication Skill	778	1	.871	1.99	1.96	Rejected
Teachers' Job Performance	778	.871	1			

The result presented on Table 4, the t-calculated value of 1.99 is greater than t-critical value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and 776 degree of freedom. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there is significant relationship between principals' application of communication skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Ho2: There is no significant relationship between principals' application of interpersonal relationship skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 5: t-test analysis of no significant relationship
 between application of interpersonal relationship skill and teachers' job performance

N		Interpersonal Relationship Skill	Teachers' Job Performance	t-cal.	t-crit.	Remark
Interpersonal Relationship Skill	778	1	.711	1.97	1.96	Rejected
Teachers' Job Performance	778	.711	1			

Data presented on Table 5, the t-calculated value of 1.97 is greater than t-critical value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and 776 degree of freedom. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there is significant relationship between principals' application of interpersonal relationship skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Ho3: There is no significant relationship between principals' application of supervisory skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State.

Table 6: t-test analysis of no significant relationship
 between application of supervisory skill and teachers' job performance

N		Supervisory Skill	Teachers' Job Performance	t-cal.	t-crit.	Remark
Supervisory Skill	778	1	.867	2.05	1.96	Rejected
Teachers' Job Performance	778	.867	1			

Result presented on Table 6, the t-calculated value of 2.05 is greater than t-critical value of 1.96 at 0.05 level of significance and 776 degree of freedom. Thus, the null hypothesis is rejected. Thus, there is significant relationship between principals' application of supervisory skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State.

5. Discussion of Findings

The findings of the study revealed that there is a high relationship between principals' application of communication skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State. This is in line agreement with the finding of Egboka and Alike (2018) which indicated there was high relationship between principals' application of communication skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State. The possible explanation for the agreement between the findings could be due to the fact that the two studies were conducted in Anambra State and utilized the same participants. The communication skills of principals which involve listening attentively and embracing the opinions of teachers create favourable working environment. The application of communication skills by principals help to give clear direction and expectation from members of staff in school. It also facilitates the dissemination of information of tasks required of teachers, when and how to execute them. This may account for remarkable improvement on teachers' job performance as evident in secondary school students academic achievement in external examinations in Anambra State. It was also reported that there was significant relationship between principals' application of communication skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State. This is supported the finding of Egboka and Alike (2018) who reported that there was significant relationship between principals' application of communication skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools. The result was not surprise to the researchers due to fact that they were conducted in the same geographical location.

The result of this study indicated that there is a moderate positive relationship between principals' application of interpersonal relationship skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State. This contradicted the finding of Giami and Obiechina (2019) who reported there was a high positive significant relationship between principals' interpersonal relationship skills and teachers' job performance in public secondary schools. The contradiction between the findings may be due to the fact that the two studies were conducted in different geographical location. Interpersonal skills of principals help them to work effectively with teachers to identify and solve problems in the school system. It also assist principals to work with, understand, and motivate teachers to execute tasks in school. This create friendly and favourable work environment for teachers to effectively perform their job. The finding of this study also revealed that there was significant relationship between principals' application of interpersonal relationship skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State. This agreed with the finding of Giami and Obiechina (2019)

which indicated that there was a statistically significant relationship between principals' interpersonal relationship skills and teachers' job performance.

It was found out that there is a high relationship between principals' application of supervisory skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State. The supervisory skills of principals help them to guide and stimulate the teachers in performing their job. It also provides opportunity for principals to clarify and resolve the challenges encountered by teachers during instructional delivery. It was also reported that there was significant relationship between principals' application of supervisory skill and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State. This is in agreement with the finding of Muraina (2014) who reported that there is no significant relationship between principals' supervisory skill and administrative and teachers effectiveness. The agreement between the findings may be due to the fact that the two studies were conducted in the same country where similar managerial skills are applied by principals. Principals supervisory skills enable them to observe classroom instructional delivery, inspect their lesson note and plan in order to render professional help that could enhance their lesson presentation.

6. Conclusion

Based on the findings, it was concluded that there was relationship between principals' application of supervisory skills and teachers' job performance in secondary schools in Anambra State. Communication, interpersonal relationship and supervisory skills applied by principals have positive relationship with teachers' job performance. This situation could account for remarkable academic performance of secondary school students in Anambra State.

6.1 Recommendations

Based on the findings, it was recommended among others that:

- 1) Post Primary School Service Commission should introduce a school-based annual training programme in all secondary schools for principals to up-date their communication skills to enhance teachers' job performance.
- 2) Ministry of Education should organize constantly and compulsory workshop for principals for interact and acquire requisite interpersonal skills for working effectively with teachers to improve their managerial efficiency and teachers' job performance.
- 3) Ministry of Education develop policy which incorporate supervisory skills to enable secondary school principals have operational document with regards to relevant skills for supervising teachers' to improve their job performance.

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